

**MASTER OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
STUDIES**
Capstone Project

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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**CANDIJAY FISHERY AND AGRICULTURAL HOUSEHOLD REGISTRATION
MANAGEMENT AND DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM (C-FARMS)**

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26 December 2022

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This paper prepared by **ALMA MAE B. AUXTERO** with the title: “**CANDIJAY FISHERY AND AGRICULTURAL HOUSEHOLD REGISTRATION MANAGEMENT AND DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM (C-FARMS)**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author conveys her sincere and profound gratitude to the following persons who have been involved and have contributed to the completion of this Capstone Project.

Dr. Proceso M. Castil, former Campus Director of Bohol Island State University Candijay Campus, for his encouragement and challenge to finish the master's degree;

Dr. Luzminda Machete, current Campus Director of Bohol Island State University Candijay Campus, for her moral support to finish the master's degree;

Dr. Arlinda N. Ramasola, dean of the College of Technology and Allied Sciences, for her valuable advice and moral support to finish the master's degree;

Mrs. Evangeline N. Olandria, chairperson of the Bachelor of Science in Computer Science Department, for her encouragement and warm support to the author;

Engr. Ermita Bual, Municipal Agriculture Officer of the Municipality of Candijay, for her assistance and accommodation during interviews and testing activities for the project;

Dr. Ria Mae H. Borromeo, for sharing her time, effort, and expert insights for the improvement of this Capstone Project;

To the beloved husband Mr. Fel Joseph C. Auxtero, for his tireless effort in critiquing the manuscript for this Capstone Project;

To the beloved youngest brother, Mr. Jasper J. Bernales, for his unending patience in teaching the author with new technologies and techniques and providing technical references for the development of C-FARMS;

To the beloved older brothers, Mr. John Albert J. Bernales and Mr. Vincent Allen J. Bernales, for their moral and spiritual support to the author;

To the beloved parents, Engr. Alberto G. Bernales and Dr. Ma. Magdalena J. Bernales, for being the constant prayer warriors and for providing moral and financial support which contributed to the completion of the master's degree;

Above all, the author thanks the Almighty God for His countless blessings, making this work a reality.

ABSTRACT

This project aims to develop the Candijay Fishery and Agricultural household Registration and Management System (C-FARMS), a decision support system to assist the Municipal Agriculture Office (MAO) in managing its programs for registered farming and fisheries households in the municipality of Candijay. The system focuses on record-keeping and program beneficiary selection to aid the MAO in fulfilling its mandate to promote agriculture and fisheries development among constituents. The project followed the Rapid Application Development model and resulted in a three-tiered web application using ReactJS, NodeJS, GraphQL API, and PostgreSQL. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was used to validate and verify the system, including administering online surveys and conducting end-to-end testing with Cypress. Results showed that users found the system to be acceptable and all test cases passed. The system is ready for deployment to the MAO, but maintenance plans should be implemented to ensure continued effectiveness.